

An Intelligent Agro-Cloud Advisory System for Smart Irrigation

Dr.S.Anitha

Assistant Professor

Department of Computer Applications
SRM Institute of Science and Technology
Tiruchirappalli - 621105 , Tamilnadu, India
anitha.s@ist.srmtrichy.edu.in

Abstract: Though agriculture is considered as the backbone of India, still farmers are struggling a lot to get profit due to water scarcity, storms, flooding, drought, etc. Moreover, farmers are not adopting modern technologies due to lack of awareness, limited land size, and expenses. The proposed agro-cloud advisory system focuses on one of the essential agricultural practices namely irrigation. Crop fields should be watered regularly for healthy crop growth. Water holding capacity differs from soil to soil. Clay soil grips higher water content than sandy soil. Measurement of water quality depends on the salt contents and their quantity in water. The irrigation timing and frequency differ from soil to soil, crop to crop, and season to season. Based on the availability of water sources like wells, tube wells, canals, lakes, rivers, and the cost, any one of the traditional methods or modern irrigation methods are employed in the field. But modern irrigation methods use water efficiently with less wastage. The proposed intelligent advisory system consists of the three main components namely i) Data collection Layer ii) Data processing Layer and iii) User interface Layer. The data collection layer gathers data from devices like sensors, meters, cameras, drones, and satellite data. In the data processing layer, the data collected from layer1 is stored & processed in a cloud. A feed forward multi layer neural network is employed to select the appropriate irrigation method like drip irrigation, sprinkler irrigation based on the type of crop, soil, source of water, rainfall, labor cost. The user interface layer provides the perspective irrigation guidelines to the farmers through notification messages, graphical user interfaces (GUI), mobile applications. The devised cloud-based smart irrigation system supports the farmers to control the functions of irrigation from remote systems and also reduces the wastage of water, labor cost, and conserving energy.

Keywords: Agro-cloud, Agriculture advisory system, Smart Irrigation, Intelligent System, Neural Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

In India, a variety of crops are grown in different regions of the country based on climatic conditions such as humidity, rainfall, and temperature. There are two major cropping patterns in India namely i) Kharif crops and ii) Rabi crops. Kharif crops are sown in the rainy session during June and harvested at the end of October. Rabi crops

are grown in the winter session from October to March. The sequence of activities performed by the farmers over some time to cultivate the crops is known as agriculture practices as depicted in figure 1.

Fig. 1. Agricultural Practices

Irrigation is one of the vital agricultural practices which monitor the moisture of the soil for crop growth. Smart irrigation aids the minimum water level for crop cultivations by employing sensors in the crop field.

The methods of irrigation are classified into two types namely i) traditional methods and ii) modern methods. In traditional methods, cattle or human labor is employed to carry from water sources to crop fields. Traditional methods are cheaper but take a lot of time and also more water wastage during irrigation. The various traditional methods are i) Moat ii) Chain pump iii) Dhekli iv) Rahat v) Furrow irrigation vi) Canal irrigation. Modern methods of irrigation utilize water more efficiently with less water wastage. The main methods of modern irrigation are i) Sprinkler system and ii) Drip system. The Sprinkler system is appropriate for uneven land with sandy soil where the water level is very low. In a sprinkler system, pipes are used to carry the water from the water sources. The rotating nozzles on the top of the pipe spray water on the crops at regular intervals as like raining. In drip irrigation, pipes are laid out over the field, and water is made to fall drop by drop directly near the roots of plants through the smaller holes. Drip irrigation is the most water-efficient method

which reduces the wastage of water through evaporation and run-off.

Nowadays, Smart irrigation is convenient and cost-effective which reduces the wastage of water through the technical advancements of IoT, cloud computing, and mobile communication. Smart irrigation helps the farmers to use water economically. In smart irrigation, scheduling of water timing and the water level will be automated based on parameters like weather data, soil conditions, and type of crop. Google trend results [1] for smart irrigation for the period 25/12/2019 to 25/12/2021 are shown in figure 2.

Fig. 2. Google trends result for Smart Irrigation

According to the smart irrigation market report [2], the smart irrigation market size will be estimated to reach \$5.57 billion by 2030 which is valued at \$1.44 billion in 2020 which is depicted in figure 3.

Fig. 3. Smart irrigation market size

Smart irrigation gives farmers remote control over essential functions of irrigation like notification about water scheduling, water leakage. Smart irrigation also helps to reduce the wastage of water, labor costs and to conserve energy. The proposed research work collects the data from the crop field, processes the continuous data, and suggests the appropriate action to the farmers.

The proposed research work is organized as follows: Section 1 introduces the significance of technological advancements in the agriculture sector; section 2 highlights the related smart

irrigation research works to reduce the wastage of water; the proposed intelligent agro-cloud-based smart irrigation system is illustrated in section 3. The design methodology of the proposed advisory system is discussed in section 4; findings and outcomes of the work are summarized in section 5; the extension work of the planned cloud-based advisory services is depicted in section 6.

II. Related Work

This section emphasizes the various technologies employed in the automation of smart irrigation to increase the productivity of crops with the minimum water levels.

Neha et al [3] proposed a neural network-based intelligent system that helps the automated water scheduling to farmers at a low cost. For augmenting communication with farmers, MQTT is applied for remote monitoring of crop growth and efficient irrigation. Benyezza et al [4] devised an IoT platform based on Thingspeak, Arduino which aids the farmers to monitor the healthy growth of crops and efficient watering through remote computers or mobile applications. Garcia et al [5] designed a 4-layer architecture for smart irrigation which exploits IoT and Wireless Sensor Networks [WSN] for crop monitoring and water schedule.

Keswani et al [6] developed an IoT-enabled WSN framework to find the geographical regions with water scarcity. The devised framework employs various devices namely soil moisture (MC) probe, temperature measuring device, temperature sensor, humidity sensor, CO₂ sensor, intensity device. Togneri et al [7] implemented a flexible architecture to combine IoT and machine learning for smart irrigation which reduces water consumption and safer crop yields. Koduru et al [8] demonstrated an IoT and cloud-based framework for smart irrigation which exploits excessive water to increase the groundwater level. This framework employs heterogeneous devices for acquiring continuous real-time data from the crop field.

Boursianis et al [9] represented an intelligent irrigation system for precision agriculture that uses energy harvesting techniques to power the IoT nodes. Sinwar et al [10] described different techniques and Artificial Intelligence for smart irrigation and better crop yield. Singhet al [11] proposed an IoT-driven framework that exploits Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning techniques to optimize irrigation water usage. Sudharshan et al [12] demonstrated a Fuzzy-logic based automated irrigation system to reduce the installation and maintenance cost by employing solar energy. The related work highlights the importance of the role of various sensors, weather data, IoT, cloud computing, and machine learning in

the automation of smart irrigation to reduce the wastage of water and healthy crop production.

III. SMART IRRIGATION SYSTEM

The proposed smart irrigation system consists of the following three layers namely i) Data collection Layer ii) Data processing Layer and iii) User interface Layer as shown in figure 4. The data collection layer acquires the data from the various sensors, mechanical devices which are installed in the crop field. In addition to the sensor data from the temperature sensor, moisture sensor, motion sensor, light sensor, and PH sensor, weather data from the satellite is also collected and forwarded to data processing layer 2. In layer 2, to store and process the continuous data, various computation technologies namely cloud computing, big data, Internet of Things, and mobile computing are employed in the smart irrigation system.

Layer 3 is the user interaction layer which provides the output to the farmers to do the appropriate action. User interaction layer can be implemented as a web application or mobile application.

Fig. 4. Agro-Cloud Advisory System for Smart Irrigation

All the three layers namely data collection layer 1, data processing layer 2, and user interface layer 3 are communicated via wireless communication.

A feed-forward neural network is employed to select the appropriate irrigation method based on the type of soil, moisture content of the soil, weather data as shown in figure 5. The feed-forward network consists of one input layer, one hidden layer, and one output layer. Neurons in the input layer are acquiring various sensor device data like temperature, humidity and weather data. The Net input y_{in} is calculated by using an adder function as shown in Equation 1.

Fig. 5. Feed forward neural network for selecting irrigation method

$$\text{Net input } y_{in} = W_{11} x_1 + W_{12} x_1 + \dots x_m W_{mn} \quad (1)$$

A sigmoidal activation function is employed to provide the output value Y in the range of 0 to 1. Output value Y helps to identify the suitable irrigation method. User interaction layer 3 provides the irrigation method, water scheduling details to the farmers through the web interface or mobile application.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

After collecting the sensor data and weather from the Internet, appropriate irrigation method like drip irrigation, sprinkler irrigation is scheduled from the multilayer feed-forward neural network as depicted in figure 6.

As a part of this advisory system, a web interface is implemented by using ASP.net 4.8 as front end and Microsoft SQL Server 2008 as backend which provides better perspective drip design guidelines to the farmers. Also, supports finding out the equipment’s need for the drip irrigation system. The proposed advisory web application provides information about drip irrigation system materials and supplies costs without visiting the drip irrigation company as shown in figure 7.

As a part of this advisory system, a web interface is implemented by using ASP.net 4.8 as front end and Microsoft SQL Server 2008 as backend which provides better perspective drip design guidelines to the farmers. Also, supports finding out the equipment’s need for the drip irrigation system. The proposed advisory web application provides information about drip irrigation system materials and supplies costs without visiting the drip irrigation company as shown in figure 7.

Fig. 6. Flowchart for Smart irrigation process

Fig. 7. Agriculture Advisory System

This agriculture advisory system aids the farmers as what are the places can the dripper line to be installed and farming methods such as commercial greenhouse farming, residential gardens, poly house farming, shade net farming, and open field farming. Moreover, guides the farmers in the water recycling process.

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed research work augments the proper scheduling of irrigation with the help of a web application or mobile application. The proposed advisory system reduces labor costs, saves water and electricity. The devised advisory system augments the irrigation efficiency with minimum water. Exploiting appropriate irrigation methods based on the type of soil, moisture content, temperature such as drip systems avoids overwatering and protects the crops from fungi.

VI. FUTURE WORK

The proposed work can be well-extended to add several useful functionalities. Instead of cloud computing, microcontrollers like Arduino, Raspberry pi can be exploited for smaller cropland. The irrigation method can be suggested based on the size of the cropland and installation cost, availability of water sources.

References

1. Smart Irrigation Market, Available at: <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/tag/smart-irrigation> accessed on 24th December 2021.
2. Google Trends for Smart Irrigation, Available at: <https://trends.google.com/trends/explore?date=2019-11-25%202021-12-25&geo=IN&q=Smart%20Irrigation> accessed on 25th December 2021.
3. Neha K. Nawandar, Vishal R. Satpute, "IoT based low cost and intelligent module for smart irrigation system", Computers and Electronics in Agriculture, Vol162,2019,Pages 979-990,ISSN 0168-1699, DOI: 10.1016/j.compag.2019.05.027.
4. H. Benyazza, M. Bouhedda, K. Djellout, and A. Saidi, "Smart Irrigation System Based Thingspeak and Arduino", International Conference on Applied Smart Systems (ICASS), 2018, pp. 1-4, DOI: 10.1109/ICASS.2018.8651993.
5. García, Laura, Lorena Parra, Jose M. Jimenez, Jaime Lloret, and Pascal Lorenz. 2020. "IoT-Based Smart Irrigation Systems: An Overview on the Recent Trends on Sensors and IoT Systems for Irrigation in Precision Agriculture", *Sensors* 20, no. 4: 1042. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20041042>.
6. Keswani, B., Mohapatra, A.G., Mohanty, A. et al. "Adapting weather conditions based IoT enabled smart irrigation technique in precision agriculture mechanisms", *Neural Computing & Applications*, 31, 277–292 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-018-3737-1>.
7. R. Togneri et al., "Advancing IoT-Based Smart Irrigation", *IEEE Internet of Things Magazine*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 20-25, December 2019, DOI: 10.1109/IOTM.0001.1900046.
8. Koduru S., Padala V.G.D.P.R., Padala P. (2019) "Smart Irrigation System Using Cloud and Internet of Things", 2nd International Conference on Communication, Computing and Networking. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 46. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-1217-5_20.
9. A. D. Boursianis et al., "Smart Irrigation System for Precision Agriculture—The AREThOU5A IoT Platform", *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 21, no. 16, pp. 17539-7547, 15 Aug.15, 2021, DOI: 10.1109/JSEN.2020.3033526.
10. Sinwar D., Dhaka V.S., Sharma M.K., Rani G. "AI-Based Yield Prediction and Smart Irrigation", *Internet of Things and Analytics for Agriculture*, Volume 2. Studies in Big Data, vol 67. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-0663-5_8.
11. G. Singh, D. Sharma, A. Goap, S. Sehgal, A. K. Shukla, and S. Kumar, "Machine Learning-based soil moisture prediction for Internet of Things based Smart Irrigation System," 2019 5th International Conference on Signal Processing, Computing, and Control (ISPC), 2019, pp. 175-180, DOI: 10.1109/ISPC48220.2019.8988313.
12. N Sudharshan, AVS Kasturi Karthik, JS Sandeep Kiran, S. Geetha, "Renewable Energy Based Smart Irrigation System", *Procedia Computer Science*, Volume 165,2019, Pages 615-623, ISSN 1877-0509, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2020.01.055>.